

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20967216

HIKAYAT MISA MELAYU: PERCEPTION OF COMICS AND PEOPLE'S NARRATIVE THROUGH CULTURAL HERITAGE AS THE CORE OF FORMING THE NUANCE OF THE IDENTITY OF MALAYSIAN SOCIETY

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Received: 12/04/2026
Accepted: 26/05/2026

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ABSTRACT

Culture is the identity of a society that has been a heritage passed down from generation to generation since civilization. The identity of a nation is not only marked by language elements, but also practices, lifestyles and beliefs that have become integral symbols of a society and country. Therefore, this study aims to strengthen and analyze the public's perception of comic products and polite narratives that are developed based on the content in Hikayat Misa Melayu as an effort to preserve polite culture through cultural heritage that supports the formation of the identity of the Malaysian society and country. Hikayat Misa Melayu was chosen as the source of study data by presenting several series of folk tales with the background of the Malay Sultanate and integrated with polite practices and values. Based on the research framework themed on the Islamic Framework that presents Sharia, Aqidah and Akhlaq, this study found that the production of polite comics and narratives based on the stories in Hikayat Misa Melayu has increased the understanding, appreciation and experience of the younger generation in general regarding polite values in everyday life. A total of 33 respondents were involved and provided feedback on the product produced through a questionnaire also conducted on all respondents involved in the project. 90% of respondents responded positively by stating that the content, knowledge, content and targets reached the appropriate level and made the project produced have a positive impact on society in raising awareness in preserving cultural heritage that has been passed down from generation to generation and is indirectly expressed in the Hikayat Misa Melayu. Thus, these findings prove that the Hikayat Misa Melayu is a reflection of the formation of polite practices which are the core of the formation of the identity of the Malaysian community and nation.

KEYWORDS: Hikayat Misa Melayu, cultural preservation, politeness, heritage, identity formation, Malaysia.

1. INTRODUCTION

Culture is an important element that shapes the identity of a society and a country. In the context of Malaysian society consisting of various races, culture is the basis for the formation of social harmony, national unity, and the identity of the people. In general, culture refers to the entire way of life practiced by a community group, including language, customs, beliefs, values, arts, food, clothing, and social behavior that is inherited from one generation to another. Culture not only reflects the history and background of a society, but also shows the level of thinking, human values, and social relationships in daily life. In the era of globalization that is increasingly developing rapidly, culture faces various challenges due to the influence of external cultures that easily permeate through social media, communication technology, digital entertainment, and changes in modern lifestyles. However, culture still plays an important role in maintaining national identity and strengthening community unity. This is because culture can be a unifying medium that connects multi-racial societies through the appreciation of the values of respect, tolerance, and cooperation.

In addition, culture is also a symbol of national heritage or a nuance of image that needs to be preserved so that it does not disappear with the times. Many traditional cultural heritages such as Khazanah, a collection of old stories Hikayat Misa Melayu, zapin dance, dikir barat, wayang kulit, ngajat dance, congkak games, and weaving arts are receiving less attention from the younger generation because they are more attracted to modern culture from abroad. If this situation continues, local cultural identity will be increasingly eroded and future generations may no longer recognize the roots of their own nation's culture. Therefore, various efforts need to be implemented to ensure that local culture continues to be preserved and passed on to the younger generation. These include strengthening cultural education in schools, organizing cultural festivals, increasing traditional arts programs, and using digital media as a medium for promoting local culture, including producing various mediums or platforms such as this study. In addition, parents also play an important role in introducing customs and culture to children from an early age so that they will appreciate their own nation's heritage more. Culture is also closely related to the formation of individual personalities because good cultural values can produce a society that is moral, disciplined, and responsible. These values need to be strengthened so that society is not influenced by negative cultures

such as extreme individualism, hedonism, and selfishness. It is clear that culture is not just a traditional heritage, but also an important foundation in the formation of identity, unity, and the well-being of society.

Apart from functioning as a symbol of identity and unity, culture also plays an important role in the development of the country's economy and tourism sector. The uniqueness of a country's culture can attract tourists from all over the world to come and learn about the lives of local communities. Malaysia, for example, is known as a country rich in cultural diversity, traditional food, performing arts, and customs of various races. Foreign tourists are not only attracted by the country's natural beauty, but they also want to experience unique cultural experiences such as watching traditional dance performances, enjoying local food, attending cultural festivals, and visiting cultural villages. This situation indirectly helps to increase the country's economy through the tourism, hospitality, transportation, and handicraft industries. Malaysia as a constitutional monarchy is also a major attraction for tourists visiting Malaysia. Therefore, with the efforts to create comics and polite narratives adapted from Hikayat Misa Melayu, this statement is further strengthened that Malaysia's old treasures are full of historical roots that can attract people to know about them.

Therefore, cultural development in the modern era needs to be implemented in a balanced way so that the original value of culture is not lost due to over-commercialization. Some parties only highlight culture for profit without understanding the true meaning behind a custom or tradition. As a result, culture becomes just entertainment and loses its true heritage value. Therefore, efforts to preserve culture need to involve cooperation between the government, educational institutions, non-governmental organizations, and local communities so that cultural development can be carried out ethically and continuously. The community also needs to be aware of the importance of preserving culture as a priceless national treasure. A well-preserved culture can not only increase the country's economy, but also strengthen the country's image in the eyes of the world. This is because a country rich in culture is often considered to have a high history, human values, and civilization. Therefore, culture needs to be seen as an important asset of the country that can contribute to social, economic, and international development.

In the context of research related to cultural preservation through visual storytelling, the communication aspect plays a very important role.

Visual storytelling is able to convey information in a more interesting and easy-to-understand way compared to delivery that only relies on text. Through the use of images, illustrations, videos or graphics, the cultural values contained in a society can be translated more effectively to various layers of the audience. This method not only helps strengthen the community's understanding of cultural heritage, but can also attract the interest of the younger generation who are more inclined to the visual medium in their daily lives.

In addition, research that utilizes visual storytelling has the potential to become a more sustainable cultural documentation medium. Many cultural elements such as customs, performing arts, handicrafts and traditional practices are increasingly facing the risk of extinction due to changing times. Therefore, efforts to document culture through visual materials can ensure that the information is recorded more completely and easily accessible in the future. In this case, the research conducted not only contributes to the development of knowledge, but also functions as a mechanism for conserving high-value heritage.

1.1. *The Concept of Folk Comics and Narrative Based on the Hikayat Misa Melayu*

The Concept of Comics and Folk Narratives, which focuses on adapting the rare manuscript of Hikayat Misa Melayu into comic form. The data collected involves manuscript text and narrative transcription. The purpose is not only to fulfill the documentation aspects of Malay history and literature, but also focuses on appreciating the values of politeness and morality contained in Hikayat Misa Melayu through the concept of comics and folk narratives. Through this development, researchers can directly see that respondents understand moral values, social interactions, and cultural norms conveyed through visual and narrative mediums.

Hikayat Misa Melayu is a historical literary work that records the story of the Sultanate of Perak by Raja Chulan Ibn Raja Hamid, including important events, political and economic structures, 'customs' and the life of its people which are written in an orderly and chronological manner. This hikayat is a symbol of the majesty of Malay heritage, especially during the reign of Sultan Iskandar Dzulkarnain, the Perak generation, to understand the history, identity, and traditions of the state in more depth. Among the things emphasized in this hikayat are the structure of the economic system, the political structure, the appointment and giving of titles to the dignitaries, the state government administration, the arts and the

'adat isti'adat' practiced at that time. This hikayat not only narrates the history of the Malays of Perak, but also details the symbols that are meaningful to the Malays, Perak.

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Figure 1: *Hikayat Misa Melayu (Raja Chulan Raja Hamid: 1966 by Penerbit Pustaka Antara).*

Figure 2: *Hikayat Misa Melayu (Raja Chulan Raja Hamid:1909 by Penerbit Pustaka Antara).*

Figure 3: *Hikayat Misa Melayu* (Edited by Prof. Dr. Jelani Harun: 2013)

Through the folk comic and narrative approach, the heritage content in the *Hikayat Misa Melayu* is reworked in a more polite, creative and easy to understand form, thus making it relevant for the younger generation without losing the originality of the values and identity of the heritage. This interactive development adapts the rare manuscript of the *Hikayat Misa Melayu* into the form of comics and narratives to creatively convey the values of politeness, manners and morality. From the perspective of comic production, this study has produced 5 comic manuscripts that are characterized by narratives from the *Hikayat Misa Melayu* such as figure 4, figure 5, figure 6, figure 7 and figure 8. The five comics and narratives developed are stories that are fully adapted through the *Hukayat Misa Melayu* and rearranged more simply without changing the original storyline and also emphasize the aspect of politeness as the heart of Malaysian society, especially the Malays who are full of customs, manners and etiquette.

Figure 4: *Production of the Comic Book Sultan Iskandar Plays in the Sea.*

Figure 5: *Production of the Comic Book Incident of the Missing Dato' in Padang.*

Figure 6: *Production of the Comic Book of Chempaka Sari.*

Figure 7: *Production of the Comic Book of the Engagement of Sultan Iskandar Dzulkarnain with the Princess of Raja Budak Rasul.*

Figure 8: Production of the Chempaka Sari Comic Book based on the Hikayat Misa Melayu

Therefore, efforts to realize the development of People's Comics and Narratives aim to instill the values of politeness, manners and character among the community through a medium that is close to the audience, especially the younger generation. Comics were chosen because of their visual, simple and easy to understand nature, while people's narratives function as a vehicle for heritage that is loaded with moral teachings, local wisdom and noble values. The combination of these two mediums allows polite messages to be delivered effectively. In the meantime, elements of polite language, civilized dialogue and wise conflict resolution are emphasized so that they can serve as role models for readers. Overall, the development of people's comics and narratives not only preserves cultural heritage, but also plays a role in shaping the character and identity of the community. Through a creative and inclusive approach, it has the potential to become an effective informal education platform, contributing to the inculturation of politeness values in daily life and strengthening the cultural identity of the nation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study by Shahul Hamid and Ghazali (2021) analyses the e-comic Hikayat Patani: Putera Pewaris Kerajaan produced by Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka based on the traditional text Hikayat Patani. Researchers use textual analysis and literature review approaches to understand how the values of Malay cultural heritage are embedded in the visual and narrative elements of the comic, as well as challenging issues such as production costs and internet access. This study shows that the e-comic has strong content in terms of Malay identity and has the potential to attract the younger generation to traditional heritage texts. Meanwhile, a study by Manouach and Foka (2025) investigates how digital comics and webcomics are forms of cultural heritage

that need to be preserved in a digital context. The authors show that the UNESCO traditional heritage framework needs to be expanded to include digitally born works such as comics, which gain meaning not only based on physical form but also through community interaction and digital platforms. This study provides an important theoretical foundation if heritage comic projects such as Hikayat Patani are viewed as cultural heritage assets that need to be immortalized digitally. Similarly, the study by Ché Ross et al. (2025) researched the collection of rare Malay manuscripts and books at Cambridge University Library, recording rare materials that are often overlooked by local researchers. These manuscripts contain a wealth of historical, cultural, and thought information about the classical Malay community, providing important data for the conservation and interpretation of traditional cultural narratives. This article is relevant as theoretical support and evidence that rare manuscripts are not just historical sources but also content sources for creative media such as comics that combine traditional texts and illustrations.

The study by Manouach, et al. (2025) using the design and development of digital comics that highlight local legends shows that the digital comic medium not only functions to document traditional stories but can also increase the younger generation's understanding of the value of cultural heritage such as folklore and its morals. The data shows a high acceptance of comics as an innovative medium in cultural education. This approach is relevant to the comic project based on the Perak manuscript because it shows a practical way to transfer oral and written traditions into a visual narrative medium. The opinion of Prihantini et. al. (2025) who also discussed the preservation of ancient Malay Nusantara manuscripts, access issues, and conservation issues of old written heritage materials. Although the focus is not on comics directly, this study provides an important context in integrating traditional manuscript texts into new media, including comics or visual adaptations, by understanding the values of the heritage that we wish to preserve as well as the challenges in the digital age.

Recent studies have shown that traditional text-based e-comics are an effective medium to engage the younger generation towards understanding cultural heritage, with strong identity values and production challenges that need to be managed (Shahul Hamid & Ghazali, 2021). Theoretical studies on comics as digital heritage emphasize the importance of comics not just as reading material but also as digital cultural

artifacts that need to be preserved in the context of contemporary heritage (Manouach & Foka, 2025). In addition, studies of rare Malay manuscripts in foreign collections highlight the inherent value of classical texts as a source of cultural content that can be adapted into creative media (Ché Ross et al., 2025). Studies on the development of digital comics for local legends demonstrate practical approaches to documenting cultural values through innovative visual narratives (Prihantini et al., 2025), while research on the preservation of ancient manuscripts provides context for efforts to manage written heritage materials as new media sources (Nofrizal, 2025). Thus, a literature review to understand the existing research landscape and identify research gaps that are still underexplored proves the need to identify and analyze the aspects of politeness that exist in the Malay Mass as part of the basis of politeness education for the Malay community in particular and Malaysia in general.

In addition, the literature discussion also emphasizes the importance of polite values, manners and morals in Malay culture which are rooted in Islamic teachings and local customs. Traditional manuscripts such as the Hikayat Misa Melayu are identified as important sources that contain these values, but their use in the context of modern education is still limited. Therefore, this study takes the initiative to adapt values from traditional works into a form that is more friendly to the current generation without affecting the authenticity of their original meaning and context. Overall, the literature review aims to provide a strong theoretical and conceptual foundation for this study and prove the need to develop comics and folk narratives based on the Hikayat Misa Melayu. Findings from previous research highlights support the need and relevance of this study, thus strengthening the justification for the selection of the study design and methodological approach used.

3. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive qualitative study was used in this study to analyze respondents' perceptions of the development of comics and folk narratives based on the Hikayat Misa Melayu which is a rare history of the state of Perak, Malaysia as a source of history and culture. The development is an educational initiative that aims to foster the values of politeness, manners, and morality among the younger generation. This study is important because it emphasizes a creative approach in conveying values through various mediums that are more interesting and easy to understand. The study uses the Misa Melayu Sejarah

Nadir Perak as the main source to build comics where the historical text in the Misa Melayu is loaded with valuable stories, proverbs, idioms, and philosophies of the Perak Malay community. By adapting this historical narrative into comics, traditional stories can be revived in a modern and easily accessible way for the younger generation, while preserving historical and cultural treasures that are increasingly marginalized in society.

In addition, this study uses a qualitative approach because it provides an opportunity to delve into the experiences, perceptions, and views of respondents about the content conveyed through comics and folk narratives. The qualitative approach was chosen because this study not only wants to understand the effectiveness but also evaluate respondents' perceptions in appreciating the values of politeness, morality, and Malay culture through creative mediums. Descriptive studies, in which researchers attempt to describe social phenomena comprehensively based on the actual experiences of respondents, while interpreting the meaning behind interactions and the application of values in the context of learning.

33 Respondents involved in this study were randomly selected by meeting the specified characteristics such as being aged 15 years and above and having accessed the materials that had been developed related to comics and folk narratives. The questionnaire provided included the respondent's background and five respondent assessments related to the materials that had been developed. Respondents first had to access the materials provided before filling out or evaluating them based on the questionnaire.

The study, which emphasizes the balance between customs, culture and Islamic law as the basis for the formation of the identity of the Malay community, is conducted based on a framework that is structured based on the principle that cultural heritage cannot be separated from religious values, in line with the Malay-Islamic philosophy of 'customs are linked to syarak, syarak is linked to Kitabullah. Therefore, each element of heritage studied is examined not only from the aspect of aesthetics and history, but also from the point of view of values, manners, and consistency with Islamic teachings. The framework of this study is centered on three main principles in Islam based on the law of the Quran and Hadith, namely (i) *aqidah*, which is faith which is the core in understanding heritage as a trust of Allah SWT that needs to be preserved. Each element of heritage, whether mosque architecture, clothing, food, music or craft art, is seen as a manifestation of the faith of

the Perak Malay community towards God and religious life. Therefore, through this study, it can help examine the continuity of cultural heritage reflecting belief, a sense of servitude and human relationship with Allah SWT.

Next, (ii) syarah, which is the rules and practices that serve as a guide in assessing the compatibility of customs and culture with Islamic law. This study also examines the continuity of Malay customs in line with the Sharia, especially in the aspects of politeness, clothing, food, mosque architecture, and social practices. The cultural elements studied are understood as practices that do not conflict with Islamic law, but rather support the formation of a civilized and moral society. Meanwhile, (iii) morality, namely values and manners that are the result of a combination of faith and Sharia. This study examines the values of politeness, manners, respect, and togetherness contained in folk narratives, rare

manuscripts, traditional songs, and the practices of 'Perak Malay customs. These moral values are the main focus in the comic and folk narrative project as a medium for transferring values to the younger generation.

The Islamic study framework is directly applied in this study to convey heritage knowledge in a polite and civilized manner as a cultural trust that also functions as a medium for transferring Islamic values and politeness to the younger generation. This Islamic study framework ensures that heritage preservation efforts are not just cultural documentation, but also a form of worship and social responsibility. By making Islam the foundation, this study contributes to the formation of a knowledgeable, moral and identity-based society and is in line with the aspirations of holistic community development as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Islamic Framework in the Development of Comics and Folk Narratives Based on Hikayat Misa Melayu.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The following discussion will detail the respondents' responses to the adaptation of the rare

manuscript of Hikayat Misa Melayu into comic and narrative form to creatively convey the values of politeness, manners, and morality. Findings show that the comic medium is effective in attracting the

attention of young participants, making the learning of politeness values more interactive and easy to understand. Questionnaire analysis shows that participants understand moral teachings, leadership values, and manners in the context of everyday life. In addition, respondents also emphasized that this approach facilitates the transfer of cultural values from previous generations to the current generation. In other words, the development of comics and folk narratives successfully emphasizes the balance between entertainment, education, and heritage preservation, in line with Islamic teachings that encourage civilized entertainment and value education.

Respondents' responses were analyzed based on a scale of 1 to 5, namely scale 1 for strongly disagree, scale 2 for disagree, scale 3 for neutral, scale 4 for agree, and scale 5 for strongly agree. Figure 7 to Figure 10 show the findings of the study regarding respondents' acceptance of learning materials based on Hikayat Misa Melayu. Overall, the majority of respondents gave a positive view of the use of the material in the teaching and learning process. This finding proves that Hikayat Misa Melayu is still relevant as a modern educational medium because it is able to attract students' interest, increase

understanding of Malay cultural values, and help develop aspects of language and critical thinking. This also shows that traditional literary heritage not only has historical value, but is still able to function as an effective educational tool in the current context.

Figure 10 shows that 78.8% of the study respondents strongly agree that the material contained in comics and Rakyat narratives meets the need to preserve cultural heritage through such a medium. While 3%, namely 1 respondent, gave a scale of 3, meaning that the material is only neutral and 18.2% gave a scale of 4, meaning that they agree with the content of the material that can increase readers' understanding of cultural heritage. This finding clearly illustrates that the use of creative mediums such as comics, illustrations and multimedia is able to increase public awareness of the importance of preserving and upholding Malay cultural treasures. In today's digital era, conventional learning approaches alone are no longer sufficient to attract the attention of the younger generation. Therefore, the combination of visual and technological elements in the presentation of Hikayat Misa Melayu can make the learning material more interactive and easy to understand.

Figure 10: Participant Responses to Material Elements Meeting Preservation Requirements

In addition, the use of multimedia also helps the process of delivering traditional stories more interestingly and effectively. Visual elements such as character illustrations, setting and storyline can help students imagine the atmosphere of the story more clearly. This situation indirectly increases students' imagination and understanding of the content of the story. At the same time, the multimedia medium can make the Hikayat Misa Melayu closer to the lives of the younger generation who are indeed exposed to the use of technology in their daily lives. This shows that almost all respondents accept the use of multimedia medium as a positive approach. This situation is important because good acceptance from users will determine the effectiveness of a learning

material.

Figure 11 shows the response of respondents to the content contained in the comics and folk narratives in accordance with the Hikayat Misa Melayu. 75.8% of respondents strongly agree that the content contained in the material is appropriate and coincides with the Hikayat Misa Melayu. While 21.2%, which is 7 respondents, gave an agree scale and 1 respondent chose a neutral scale.

Tables, just like figures should be captioned and styled with SC-Table-Caption as shown in Table I. Table captions are placed above the table and centred. Tables must also be referenced in the text, either manually or by using the 'Cross-reference' function of the word processing software (just like in

the case of figures).

Figure 11: Participant Responses to the Filling Elements in the Malay Mass Story

This finding proves that the approach of adapting folk tales and traditional hikayats in a more modern form has successfully attracted the attention of the public, especially the young. Adapting traditional narratives to a more contemporary form is very important to ensure that classic works remain relevant. The Hikayat Misa Melayu originally used classical language which is quite difficult for the current generation to understand. Therefore, the process of adapting the language and presenting the story can help readers understand the content of the hikayat more easily without losing the original value of the work. This approach allows the public to recognize the heritage of Malay literature in a more user-friendly form. In addition to facilitating understanding, narrative adaptation also helps maintain readers' interest in traditional works. If a hikayat is presented in a form that is too formal and difficult to understand, it is likely that the younger generation will be less interested in approaching it. However, when the hikayat is processed in a more

relaxed, creative and interactive form, the public will be more encouraged to read and appreciate the work. Therefore, the use of appropriate narratives is very important in efforts to preserve the continuity of traditional Malay literature.

Figure 12 shows that 25 out of 33 respondents stated that they strongly agreed that their knowledge increased or increased after reading the comics and people's narratives which were more relaxed compared to the original Hikayat Misa Melayu manuscript which was loaded with the use of terminology, Palace language and old Malay. They added that through the comics, it was not only interactive but also the content was easier to understand and indirectly increased their understanding of polite values, moral teachings, leadership values and so on. Meanwhile, 7 of the respondents, equivalent to 21.2%, gave a scale of 4, which means they agreed that it was able to improve and 3% stated that the increase in understanding was only neutral.

Figure 12: Participant Responses to Understanding Enhancement Elements

This finding proves that learning materials based on Hikayat Misa Melayu are not just entertainment, but also function as an effective cultural education medium. Hikayat Misa Melayu is indeed rich in the use of terminology, courtly language and values of traditional Malay society. Through reading hikayats,

students can understand the culture of the Malay society in more depth. For example, they can get to know the traditional government system, customs, family relationships and the way of life of the community in the past. This kind of knowledge is very important in the effort to form a national

identity and foster a spirit of love for the country's cultural heritage. In the context of education, the application of local cultural elements can also help students appreciate their origins and identity. This finding explains that Hikayat Misa Melayu which is expressed through comics and folk narratives can help respondents understand the concepts of leadership, sacrifice and struggle of traditional Malay society. The characters in hikayats are usually depicted as having heroic qualities and a high fighting spirit. Values like this can inspire the younger generation to build a strong identity and have a spirit of patriotism. In a modern world full of challenges, the application of positive values through literary works is very important to produce a society with integrity and authority.

In addition, Hikayat Misa Melayu also contains various noble values that can be used as a guide in life. Among the values that are often highlighted are

courage, loyalty, responsibility, respect and wisdom. These values are important in shaping the character of students who have noble character. Therefore, the use of hikayat in education not only helps intellectual development, but also contributes to the emotional and moral development of students.

Figure 13 shows that 75.8% of respondents strongly agree and are beginning to realize the importance of efforts to preserve cultural heritage through the development of comics and folk narratives as implemented in this study. While 18.2%, which is 6 respondents, also agree and 6.1%, which is 2 respondents, are neutral. This aspect of importance is often overlooked by society because awareness is increasingly thin, especially involving heritage because they are more inclined to follow foreign cultures that are said to be more modern and fresh.

Figure 13: Participant Responses to Elements of Awareness of the Importance of Cultural Heritage Preservation

This finding proves that society is increasingly aware of the importance of preserving cultural heritage so that it does not disappear in the current of modernization. In the era of globalization, foreign culture is increasingly easy to influence society through mass media and communication technology. This situation has caused some of the younger generation to be less familiar with the traditional culture of their own nation. Therefore, efforts to produce learning materials based on Hikayat Misa Melayu in a modern form are a very important step to ensure that cultural heritage continues to be preserved. This approach not only helps introduce Malay culture to the younger generation, but can also prevent traditional works from being forgotten.

The findings of Figure 14 also show that respondents are more likely to accept materials that are presented creatively and interactively. A total of 78.82% of respondents strongly agree and 15.2% agree that interest in the material depends on the method of presentation. This proves that the method of presentation plays an important role in determining the effectiveness of a learning material. Materials that are too dense and formal may not attract students' attention, while materials that are light, interactive and have interesting illustrations are more easily accepted compared to 6.1% neutral. This number shows that respondents' interest in the content of the material produced must be interactive, light, easy to read and have interesting illustrations.

Figure 14: Participant responses regarding Elements of Interest towards the Materials produced.

The integration of Hikayat Misa Melayu in multimedia medium shows a significant development in efforts to strengthen the preservation of traditional Malay literary heritage. In the context of education and current technological developments, a multimedia-based approach not only functions as an entertainment medium, but also becomes an effective pedagogical channel to introduce traditional cultural and literary values to the younger generation. The transformation of traditional works into more contemporary forms such as digital comics, animation and interactive narratives allows classic works to be presented in a more interesting and easily understood way by modern society.

The use of multimedia elements in the presentation of Hikayat Misa Melayu can increase the level of user engagement with learning content. The visual, audio and interactivity elements applied in learning materials can create a more dynamic reading experience and are not limited to a purely textual approach. This situation is in line with the development of 21st century education which emphasizes the use of digital technology to enrich the teaching and learning process. Through such an approach, the content of the hikayat which was previously considered difficult to understand due to the use of classical language can now be translated in a more reader-friendly form without affecting the aesthetic and cultural values of the original work.

In addition, the use of creative mediums in the presentation of traditional hikayats also plays an important role in fostering public awareness of the importance of preserving Malay culture. Hikayat works contain various cultural elements such as customs, social systems, heroic values and philosophy of life of traditional Malay society. Therefore, efforts to present the content in a medium that is more suitable for current developments allow the community, especially the younger generation, to recognize and appreciate the cultural heritage of their own nation. This approach indirectly helps to reduce the gap between the older and younger generations in understanding the treasures of traditional literature.

The adaptation of traditional narratives to more modern forms also shows the ability of classic works to remain relevant in the era of globalization. In fact, today's society is more inclined towards reading materials that are visual, interactive and easily accessible through digital technology. Therefore, the transformation of Hikayat Misa Melayu to a multimedia medium can be considered a form of

cultural innovation that is able to ensure the continuity of traditional works in the life of modern society. The adaptation process does not mean changing the original identity of the hikayat, but rather aims to make the content of traditional literature more easily accepted and understood by contemporary audiences.

In the context of education, the use of Hikayat Misa Melayu as a learning material can provide various benefits to students. The content of the hikayat not only introduces aspects of Malay history and culture, but also helps enrich language proficiency and improve critical thinking skills. Through reading and appreciating the hikayat, students can understand the structure of classical language, the use of beautiful language styles and symbolic elements contained in traditional works. This situation can help students develop linguistic abilities and appreciation of the beauty of the Malay language.

In addition, Hikayat Misa Melayu also contains various noble values that are relevant in shaping the character of society. Elements such as courage, loyalty, wisdom, responsibility and fighting spirit are often displayed through the main characters in the hikayat. These values have great potential to be used as a medium for moral education and identity formation among students. In an era influenced by various social challenges and external cultures, the application of traditional values through local literary works is very important to form a generation with a strong national identity.

Apart from the aspect of personality formation, appreciation of traditional hikayat also helps to expand students' knowledge about the life system of the past Malay society. Hikayat often depicts the structure of government, family relationships, customs and social norms that are the basis of traditional community life. Exposure to these elements can increase students' understanding of the history of the development of Malay civilization and the importance of preserving cultural heritage as part of the national identity.

In a broader dimension, efforts to introduce Hikayat Misa Melayu through digital mediums can also contribute to the development of the local creative industry. Adapting traditional works to the form of comics, animations and interactive applications opens up opportunities for the production of creative content based on local culture. This approach is not only able to strengthen the country's creative industry, but can also introduce Malay heritage to the international level through the

use of digital platforms. In other words, traditional literature is no longer limited to printed reading materials, but has the potential to develop as a cultural product that has economic and educational value.

However, efforts to modernize Hikayat Misa Melayu need to be carried out carefully so as not to eliminate the authenticity and traditional value of the work. The adaptation process must maintain the essence of the story, cultural values and original messages contained in the hikayat. If modifications are made excessively, there is a possibility that the true identity of the traditional work will be eroded. Therefore, the production of multimedia materials based on hikayat requires in-depth research so that a balance between traditional and modern elements can be maintained.

In an effort to ensure the effectiveness of using Hikayat Misa Melayu as a learning medium, support from educational institutions and related parties is essential. Teachers, lecturers and researchers including government agencies such as the Perak Islamic Religious and Customary Council (MAIPK) and others need to play an active role in introducing traditional works to students through a more innovative approach and in line with current technological developments. The use of digital platforms, interactive materials and multimedia-based learning applications can help increase students' interest in traditional literature which is often considered difficult and boring.

Furthermore, the integration of Hikayat Misa Melayu in the education system can strengthen the position of the Malay language as a language of knowledge and a language of culture. The hikayat works show the richness of vocabulary, subtlety of language style and high aesthetic value in the Malay literary tradition. Therefore, appreciation of the works can help the younger generation understand the beauty of the Malay language more deeply. At the same time, this effort also contributes to the preservation of the nation's intellectual heritage which is increasingly marginalized due to the dominance of foreign cultures.

In conclusion, the use of multimedia medium in introducing Hikayat Misa Melayu is a relevant and significant approach in efforts to preserve the Malay cultural heritage in the modern era. This approach not only increases public interest in traditional works, but also helps strengthen understanding of cultural values, history and national identity. In addition, the use of creative and interactive materials also makes the learning process more effective and in line with current educational needs. Therefore,

various parties need to work together to ensure that Malay literary heritage continues to be preserved and passed on to future generations as a valuable cultural treasure.

5. CONCLUSION

Although culture has various importance in the life of society and the development of the country, culture also faces major challenges today due to the influence of globalization and rapid technological advancement. Today's young generation is more exposed to foreign culture through the internet, social media, international films, digital games, and modern entertainment that is easily accessible without limits. This situation has caused some of them to become less familiar with local culture and are more likely to imitate foreign cultures in the way they dress, speak, entertain, and live. If left unchecked, this phenomenon can cause local culture to become increasingly marginalized and eventually disappear in the tide of modernization. In addition, changing patterns of busy modern life have also caused society to practice old traditions less and less.

Relationships between generations are also becoming more strained when young people interact less with their elders, who are the main source of cultural inheritance. Therefore, various proactive measures need to be taken to ensure that culture continues to be preserved and appreciated by society, especially the younger generation. These include the use of digital technology to document and promote local culture through videos, social media, educational applications, and online streaming platforms. This approach is important because the younger generation is closer to technology and digital media in their daily lives. In addition, the government can expand the organization of cultural programs in schools, institutions of higher learning, and local communities to increase public awareness of the importance of culture.

Dalam konteks pendidikan pula, subjek berkaitan budaya dan warisan perlu diperkukuh supaya pelajar memahami sejarah serta kepentingan budaya dalam pembentukan identiti negara. Masyarakat juga perlu mengamalkan sikap terbuka dan menghormati budaya kaum lain bagi mengelakkan konflik sosial serta memperkukuh perpaduan nasional. Sikap saling menghormati budaya dapat mewujudkan masyarakat yang harmoni, aman, dan bersatu padu walaupun terdiri daripada latar belakang yang berbeza. Sesungguhnya, budaya merupakan khazanah yang amat bernilai dan tidak boleh dipandang ringan oleh mana-mana pihak. Budaya bukan sahaja mencerminkan identiti bangsa,

malah menjadi asas kepada pembentukan masyarakat yang bertamadun dan negara yang stabil. Oleh itu, semua pihak perlu memainkan peranan secara bersama-sama untuk memelihara, menghargai, dan memartabatkan budaya agar warisan tersebut terus kekal relevan dan dapat

diwariskan kepada generasi akan datang. Jika budaya terus dipelihara dengan baik, maka masyarakat akan lebih memahami asal usul, menghargai kepelbagaian, dan memiliki semangat cinta akan negara yang lebih kukuh pada masa hadapan.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft: Pelet, M. N. M. Investigation, Validation, Data curation, Writing- review and editing: Sarudin, A.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS: This research was funded by the Distinguished Research Grant (2025-0113-106-10) provided by Majlis Agama Islam dan Adat Melayu Perak.

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